

Mesogenic Homologous Series : 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-alkoxycinnamates and Binary Systems Comprising the Homologues of this Series

R. A. VORA^a and P. R. VYAS^{b*}

^aApplied Chemistry Department, Faculty of Technology and Engineering, M. S. University of Vadodara, Vadodara-390 001

^bCentral Laboratory, Indian Petrochemicals Corporation Limited P O Petrochemicals, Vadodara-391 346

Manuscript received 27 October 1994 accepted 16 February 1995

Twelve members of the homologous series-A have been synthesised. First two members are non-mesogenic. The nematic mesophase commences as a monotropic phase from n-propoxy derivative.

Series-A (where n = 1 to 16)

n-Propoxy to n-heptyloxy derivatives exhibit only nematic phase. n-Octyloxy and n-decyloxy derivatives exhibit smectic and nematic phases. n-Dodecyloxy to n-hexadecyloxy derivatives exhibit only smectic phase.

Seven binary systems comprised of homologues of series-A have been studied. The non-mesogens induce mesomorphism in a few binary systems. Other binary systems, where both the components are mesogens, exhibit normal behaviour of mesogenic binary systems. Results indicate that even though homologues of series-A contain branched alkyl chain, the binary systems do not exhibit pronounced decrease in melting behaviour.

In continuation of our work, one more mesogenic homologous series has been synthesised with cinnamoyloxy moiety and terminal isopropoxy group in search of new mesogens and to evaluate the effect of branched alkoxy group on mesomorphism. Moreover, it was proposed to study some binary systems incorporating mesogenic and non-mesogenic homologues of the series-A.

Results and Discussion

First two members of the series-A are non-mesogenic. The nematic mesophase commences as a monotropic phase from n-propoxy derivative. n-Propoxy to n-heptyloxy derivatives exhibit only nematic phase. n-Octyloxy and n-decyloxy derivatives exhibit smectic and nematic phases. n-Dodecyloxy to n-hexadecyloxy derivatives exhibit only smectic phase.

The plot of transition temperatures versus number of carbon atoms in the alkoxy group exhibits normal odd-even effect for nematic-isotropic transition temperatures (Fig. 1, Table 1). The smectic-nematic transition temperature curve rises and merges with the smectic-isotropic transition temperature curve which levels off in the last homologues. The smectic-nematic transition temperatures do not exhibit odd-even effect because of the late commencement of the phase in the homologous series.

The present homologous series has lower mesogenic thermal stability compared to other homologous series having similar structural features but which differed from series-A in the aspect of terminal alkoxy group at one end of

Fig. 1 Series-A, 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-alkoxycinnamates: (---) solid-isotropic or mesomorphic, (O) nematic-isotropic, (Δ) smectic-nematic and (□) smectic-isotropic.

the molecule. The series with ethoxy and n-propoxy substituent in place of isopropoxy substituent in series-A exhibits higher smectic and nematic thermal stabilities¹. This behaviour is expected as molecules of the series-A have a terminal isopropoxy group which increases the breadth of the molecules adversely affecting the stability of both the mesophases². This indicates that in conformation to car-

TABLE 1—SERIES-A : TRANSITION TEMPERATURE

n-Alkyl group	Transition temp. (°C)		
	Smectic	Nematic*	Isotropic
Methyl	-	-	99
Ethyl	-	-	145
Propyl	-	(106)*	109
Butyl	-	(109)	110
Pentyl	-	(98)	103
Hexyl	-	(102.5)	103
Heptyl	-	96	98.5
Octyl	82	87	99
Decyl	73	90	96
Dodecyl	84	-	94
Tetradecyl	83	-	91
Hexadecyl	82	-	89

*Values in parenthesis indicate monotropy.

lier work, the α -methyl group affects smectic and nematic thermal stability. However, the α -methyl terminal substituent in the molecules of the series-A does not affect solid-mesomorphic transition temperatures adversely. This is difficult to explain. Only detailed crystal structure analysis of crystal phase of the homologous series-A can help in finding the explanation.

Seven binary systems studied are classified into four groups as follows : Gr. I non-mesogen + non-mesogen; Gr. II non-mesogen + nematogen (monotropy); Gr. III nematogen + nematogen; Gr. IV polymesomorph + nematogen or smectogen.

Gr. I Non-mesogen + non-mesogen. Binary system no. 1: (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-methoxycinnamate (IPC-1) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-ethoxycinnamate (IPC-2)—both the components are non-mesogens with melting points 99 and 145° respectively. The binary system induces nematic mesophase at 10 mole% of IPC-2 in monotropy and with increase in its concentration, the nematic-isotropic transition curve rises upto 60 mole% of IPC-2 (Fig. 2, Table 2). With further increase in the concentration, the system loses mesomorphic characteristic. The melting point

Fig. 2. Binary system no. I. (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-methoxycinnamate (IPC-1) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-ethoxycinnamate (IPC-2) : (●) solid-isotropic and (O) nematic-isotropic.

TABLE 2—BINARY SYSTEM NO. 1

(A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-methoxycinnamate (IPC-1)

(B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-ethoxycinnamate (IPC-2)

Mole% of B	Transition temp. (°C)	
	Nematic	Isotropic
0	-	99
9.59	(92)*	98
19.26	(96)	104
29.09	(102)	113
38.92	(106)	120
48.88	(106)	123
58.94	(114)	131
69.04	-	136
79.25	-	138
89.62	-	142
100	-	145

*Value in parenthesis indicates monotropy.

curve drops initially but after this it shows rising tendency as the mole% of IPC-2 increases.

Gr. II Non-mesogen + nematogen (monotropy). Binary system no. II : (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-methoxycinnamate (IPC-1) and (B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-propoxycinnamate (IPC-3)—here IPC-1 is a non-mesogen and IPC-3 monotropic nematic. The phase diagram (Fig. 3, Table 3) shows that 10 mole% concentration of IPC-3 is enough to transform non-mesogenic characteristic of IPC-1 into nematic mesophase in monotropy and with 28 mole% concentration the monotropy gets transformed into enantiotropy. However, when the concentration reaches the value of 89%, the enantiotropy gets transformed back into monotropy. The maximum mesophase length of 22° is exhibited at 38 mole% concentration of IPC-3. The enantiotropic nematic phase is observed in this binary phase diagram where the depression of solid-mesomorphic temperature is maximum—almost a plateau is observed (Fig. 3).

Binary system no. III. Non-mesogen + nematogen (monotropic): (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-ethoxycinnamate

Fig. 3. Binary system no. II. (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-methoxycinnamate (IPC-1) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-propoxycinnamate (IPC-3) : (●) solid-isotropic or mesomorphic and (O) nematic-isotropic.

TABLE 3—BINARY SYSTEM NO. II

(A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-methoxycinnamate (IPC-1)
(B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-propoxycinnamate (IPC-3)

Mole% of B	Transition temp. (°C)	
	Nematic	Isotropic
0	—	99
9.22	(92)*	95
18.70	(90)	91
28.17	81	99
37.96	75	97
47.83	78	97
57.95	85	99
68.17	89	99
78.56	93	101
89.25	(103)	104
100	(106)	109

*Value in parenthesis indicates monotropy.

(IPC-2) and (B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-propoxycinnamate (IPC-3) — the phase diagram (Fig. 4, Table 4) indicates that solid-isotropic transition temperature curve exhibits almost a straight-line joining the melting points of both the components. The monotropic nematic phase continues upto 60 mole% concentration of non-mesogenic component A (IPC-2). It is observed that methoxy homologue (IPC-1) enhances nematic phase and it becomes enantiotropic in nature (binary system no. II). Ethoxy homologue could not induce enantiotropic nematic phase in similar mixture (binary system no. III). The study of these three binary systems indicates that methoxy homologue (IPC-1) though non-mesogenic, induces mesomorphism in the non-mesogens and monotropic mesogens.

Fig 4 Binary system no III (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-ethoxycinnamate (IPC-2) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-propoxycinnamate (IPC-3): (●) solid-isotropic and (○) nematic-isotropic.

*G*₁ III Nematogen + nematogen Binary system no IV Nematogen + nematogen (both monotropic) : (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-butoxycinnamate (IPC-4) and (B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-amyloxycinnamate (IPC-5). The molecular forces are not altered much as seen from the monotropy persisting throughout and the mesophase length varying between 1 and 5° (Fig. 5, Table 5).

Binary System no. V Nematogen (monotropic) + nematogen : (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-hexyloxy-

TABLE 4—BINARY SYSTEM NO. III

(A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-ethoxycinnamate (IPC-2)
(B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-propoxycinnamate (IPC-3)

Mole% of B	Transition temp. (°C)	
	Nematic	Isotropic
0	—	145
9.64	—	142
19.29	—	139
29.07	—	133
39.01	(121)*	131
48.91	(115)	126
59.02	(111)	121
69.12	(116)	118
79.38	(111)	113
89.63	(110)	111
100	(106)	109

*Value in parenthesis indicates monotropy.

Fig. 5 Binary system no IV (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-butoxycinnamate (IPC-4) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-amyloxycinnamate (IPC-5) : (●) solid-isotropic and (○) nematic-isotropic

TABLE 5—BINARY SYSTEM NO. IV

(A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-butoxycinnamate (IPC-4)
(B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-amyloxycinnamate (IPC-5)

Mole% of B	Transition temp. (°C)	
	Nematic	Isotropic
0	(109)*	110
9.65	(108)	109
19.54	(107)	108
28.95	(105)	106
39.13	(104)	105
49.17	(102.5)	104
58.95	(103)	104
68.95	(102)	103
79.25	(101)	103
89.85	(99)	103
100	(98)	103

*Value in parenthesis indicates monotropy

cinnamate (IPC-6) and (B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-heptyloxycinnamate (IPC-7) — here both the components A and B are nematogens, the former is monotropic nematic. Monotropy of the component IPC-6 gets transformed into enantiotropy with about 4 mole% of IPC-7 and persists upto the right side of the phase diagram (Fig. 6, Table 6). This indicates that the molecular forces conducive to nematogens are enhanced.

*G*₁ IV Polymesomorph + nematogen or smectogen

Fig. 6. Binary system no. V. (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-hexyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-6) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-heptyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-7) : (●) solid-isotropic or mesomorphic and (○) nematic-isotropic.

TABLE 6—BINARY SYSTEM NO. V

(A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-hexyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-6)

(B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-heptyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-7)

Mole% of B	Transition temp. (°C)	
	Nematic	Isotropic
0	(102.5)*	103
3.80	103	105
9.65	102	104
10.47	102	104
13.70	102	104
19.45	101	103
29.21	100	103
39.13	99	102
49.08	98	101
59.11	97	100
64.42	96	99
69.26	96	99
79.43	96	99
89.73	96	99
100	96	98.5

*Value in parenthesis indicates monotropy.

Binary system no. VI. Nematogen + polymesomorph : (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-heptyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-7) and (B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-octyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-8)—here IPC-7 is a nematogen while IPC-8 polymesomorph. Nematic-isotropic transition temperatures (N-I) of both the components differ by 0.5°, with the result that the mixed N-I transition curve deviates little from the ideal linearity behaviour (Fig. 7, Table 7). The system exhibits smectic mesophase in monotropy when the concentration of IPC-8 reaches 39 mole%. However, at about 50 mole% concentration, the mixed smectic-nematic (S-N) transition curve crosses into the enantiotropic region.

The mixed solid-mesomorphic (K-M) transition curve falls sharply as the concentration of IPC-8 increases till it reaches the eutectic composition registering a fall of 22° from left side of the phase diagram. The smectic phase length of 11.5° and total mesophase length of 26.5° are maximum at this eutectic composition. Extrapolation of the S-N transition curve to the left side of the phase dia-

Fig. 7. Binary system no. VI. (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-heptyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-7) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-octyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-8) : (●) solid-mesomorphic, and (○) nematic-isotropic and (Δ) smectic-nematic.

TABLE 7—BINARY SYSTEM NO. VI

(A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-heptyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-7)

(B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-octyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-8)

Mole% of B	Transition temp. (°C)		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
0	—	96	98.5
9.65	—	94	98
19.31	—	91	97
29.38	—	88	98
39.13	(82)*	86	99
49.07	(83)	83	99
58.97	80	84	99
69.35	78	84	99
79.20	76	84	100
90	75	85	100
100	82	87	99

*Value in parenthesis indicates monotropy.

gram gives latent smectic transition temperature 81° for IPC-7.

Binary system no. VII. Polymesomorph + smectogen : (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-decyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-10) and (B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-dodecyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-12)—here IPC-10 is a polymesomorph while IPC-12 is a smectogen. The upper transitions, nematic-isotropic and smectic-isotropic (N-I, S-I) of both the components differ only by 2° and the mixed N-I/S-I and smectic-nematic (S-N) transition curves almost run parallel except at the right-hand-side of the phase diagram (Fig. 8, Table 8).

The results indicate that terminal isopropoxy substituent does not exhibit any marked effect on the depression of melting points (K-I or K-M) with a few exceptions as expected from the branched chain of the isopropoxy group. Binary systems incorporating non-mesogens exhibited induced phases where methoxy homologue exhibited enhanced nematogenic character compared to ethoxy homologue as one of the components. The polymesogen and mesogen containing binary systems did not exhibit any dramatic effect in inducing smectic or nematic characteristics. The nematic phase exhibits the threaded texture while the smectic phase exhibits smectic A focal conic fan shaped texture under the polarising microscope.

Fig 8 Binary system no VII (A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-decyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-10) and (B) 4-isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-dodecyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-12) (●) solid-mesomorphic (○) nematic-isotropic (Δ) smectic nematic and (□) smectic isotropic

TABLE 8-BINARY SYSTEM NO VII

(A) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-decyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-10)

(B) 4-Isopropoxyphenyl-4'-n-dodecyloxy-cinnamate (IPC-12)

Mole% of B	Transition temp (°C)		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
0	73	90	96
4.54	70	86.5	93
9.44	76	87	92
19.02	75	86	92
28.70	74	86	92
38.51	74	89	92
48.44	75	89	92
58.50	77	93	97
65.69	79	94	97
78.97	80	94	96.5
89.44	82	95	96.5
94.62	83	-	96
100	84	-	94

Experimental

The series 4-isopropoxyphenyl 4'-n-alkoxycinnamates. These were synthesised by the following route

4-Isopropoxyphenol³ (X), 4-n-alkoxybenzaldehydes⁴, trans-4-n-alkoxycinnamic acids⁵ and trans-4-n-alkoxy-cinnamoyl chlorides⁶ were prepared by reported methods. The esters were prepared by esterification of the acid chlorides (Y) with 4-isopropoxyphenol (X) in pyridine⁷, and

where R = C_nH_{2n+1} n = 1 to 16

were purified by crystallisation from absolute ethanol. The compounds were characterised by C and H analyses which were found satisfactory. The transition temperatures (determined by using Laborlux 12 POL microscope provided with a heating stage) are recorded in Table 1.

Preparation of mixtures: Both the components of the mixtures were weighed accurately in known proportions and melted together in fusion tubes. The melt was thoroughly mixed to obtain a homogeneous mass. The melt was quenched and the mass obtained was ground finely and used for determining transition temperatures.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P R V) is thankful to Head Applied Chemistry Department, for facilities, and to Indian Petrochemicals Corporation Limited for the permission to carry out the research work and for the sponsorship to present this paper at the 14th International Liquid Crystal Conference at Pisa (1992).

References

- 1 Y K AGRAWAL and P R VYAS *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst* 1991 **209** 243
- 2 G W GRAY *Mol Cryst* 1966 **1** 333
- 3 E KIARMANN, L W GAIJAS and V A SHIERNOI *J Am Chem Soc* 1932 **54** 298
- 4 G N VYAS and N M SHAH *Org Synth* 1963 **4**
- 5 G W GRAY and B JONLS *J Chem Soc* 1954 1467
- 6 J S DAVE and R A VORA *Mol Cryst Liq Cryst* 1974 **28** 269
- 7 J S DAVE and R A VORA *Liquid Crystals* "Proc Int Conf ed S CHANDRASEKHAR Hydén 1975 p 447